

1 **Evaluating the Effectiveness of Different Household Washing Techniques for Removal of**
2 **Insecticides from Spinach and Chickpea Leaves by Micellar Liquid Chromatography**

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24

25 **Abstract**

26 In the past few decades, the employment of green analytical approaches in
27 chromatographic method development has attracted the analytical community. The greenness of
28 the developed method depends upon the toxicity of solvents and the amount of generated post-
29 analysis waste. In this concern, micellar liquid chromatography (MLC) is a simple and rapid
30 technique that generates very low toxic waste compared to traditional chromatographic pesticide
31 detection methods. Here, MLC method has been validated and applied for the determination of
32 monochrotophos (MCF), imidacloprid (ICP), dimethoate (DM) and profenofos (PFF) in spinach
33 and chickpea leaves. The optimized mobile phase in this method was 0.065 M SDS-2% 1-
34 propanol, 0.01 M NaH₂PO₄ buffered to pH 7. A C₁₈ column was used to run the mobile phase at 1
35 mL/min. The developed method has been validated following the guidelines of
36 SANTE/11,312/2021 and ICH guidelines of; limit of quantification (0.05-0.20 mg/kg), linearity
37 ($r^2 > 0.997-0.999$), precision (<6.3%), accuracy (96.3%–99.8%) and robustness (<6) in real
38 samples. ICP and MCF, apart from DM and PFF, were detected here. After detecting insecticides
39 in spinach and chickpea leaves both were washed with different household chemicals i.e. normal,
40 lukewarm, common salt, lemon juice water and commercial ozonizer. Based on five different
41 washing techniques with time intervals reduction rates were calculated for each washing treatment.
42 The results show that acidic wash, basic wash, and ozonizer can be used as washing techniques for
43 the reduction of superficial and systematic residues of ICP and MCF. But common salt and lemon
44 water have the benefit over vinegar and KMnO₄ in the aspect that it will result in a bright colour
45 on the green leafy vegetables after the treatment and are available in every kitchen and also have
46 excess to lower socioeconomic classes which could not afford potassium permanganate and
47 vinegar.

48 **Keywords:** Washing, micellar liquid chromatography, residue, insecticide

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50 1. Introduction

51 In our daily diet, vegetables are included as “protective foods” because they have various health
52 benefits and are rich in vitamins, amino acids, dietary fiber, essential fatty acids, minerals, and
53 many other essential bioactive compounds [1]. Vegetables also have health-promoting constituents
54 like antioxidants and phenolic compounds which are secondary metabolites of plants [2]. The
55 World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that at least 400g of fruits and vegetables should
56 be consumed to meet our recommended daily allowance (RDA) of nutrition [3,4], whereas the
57 American Dietary Guidelines recommends daily five servings of vegetables equivalent to 2,000
58 calories of daily intake [5]. Globally, crop diversity and the nutritional value of vegetables are
59 particularly important for improving food and its nutrition [4].

60 Spinach (*Spinacia oleracea* L.) is one of the most popular green leafy vegetable (GLV)
61 available worldwide and is commonly known as “paalak” in India [6]. It is either consumed in raw
62 form as salad or cooked into different delicacies. It is widely known as a functional food due to its
63 nutritional value. Apart from this, spinach has other beneficial properties and is considered to be
64 an anti-cancer, anti-obesity, hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic agent, etc. [7]. After common beans
65 (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) and peas (*Pisum sativum* L.), chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) is the third
66 most important winter food legume. Based on global production estimates it is mainly grown in
67 India, North Africa, the Middle East, Southern Europe, Asia, America, and Australia [8,9]. Besides
68 the seed of chickpea, the young chickpea leaves locally known as “chanabhaaji” is also consumed
69 in cooked form as GLVs in India and Nepal. Fresh chickpea leaves are considered a good source
70 of minerals [9].

71 These leafy vegetables are also consumed in cooked or half-cooked forms [11]. Like any
72 other GLVs, these are also prone to attack by pests, insects, weeds, mites, nematodes, etc. which

73 results in low quality and quantity of yield [12]. To get rid of these pests use of pesticides in
74 agriculture is common and is practiced by the majority of farmers to obtain high-quality yields
75 [13]. Almost all vegetables contain traces of pesticides; when consumed, they reach our bodies,
76 which may cause severe chronic health issues such as neurological, reproductive, respiratory,
77 cardiac, and carcinogenic [14,15].

78 Due to growing awareness of the harmful effects of pesticides/insecticides, developed and
79 developing countries have fixed the maximum residue limit (MRL) for pesticide application on
80 crops which is generally the legally tolerable level of pesticide in food that comes under good
81 agricultural practices [16]. These good agricultural practices are governed by several pesticide
82 regulatory bodies such as the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA), United
83 States Food and Drug Administration (USFDA), European Union (EU), European Commission
84 (EC), Codex Alimentarius Commission (Codex), etc. Food is considered safe and of good quality
85 when the pesticide residue level is within MRL [17,18]. But in the present day scenario, many
86 developing and under-developed countries are using highly toxic pesticides in agriculture to attain
87 high yields from crop of better quality which include monocrotophos (MCF), dimethoate (DM),
88 imidacloprid (ICP), carbendazim (CBZ), cypermethrin (CYPER), profenofos (PFF), chlorpyrifos
89 (CP) etc. MCF has been banned for use in vegetables in India by the Ministry of Agriculture since
90 10th October 2005 [19] but is still being used whereas CP is also prohibited by the Environmental
91 Protection Agency (2018) and used in the unabated form. Research on GLVs, fruits, and plants
92 has shown that ICP, MCF, CP and DM penetrate plant, fruit, and vegetable tissues and have
93 residual activity. ICP also exhibits translaminar movement in plants and can penetrate the leaf
94 cuticles. On the other hand, no residual studies have been found for PFF.

95 To get rid of residual pesticides washing is the most important step [20]. In India, GLVs
96 are generally washed with normal tap water due to which the pesticide residues are not completely
97 removed. In this work to study the effectiveness of washing for the removal of insecticides, two
98 GLVs were selected i.e., spinach and chickpea leaves. Spinach is the most consumed GLV in the
99 world and always remains at a risky level for pesticide treatment due to its higher water content.
100 Chickpea leaves are consumed mainly in rural areas of Central and North India.

101 In this work, the effectiveness of household washing techniques was employed for the
102 determination of the most commonly used insecticide i.e., MCF, ICP, DM and PFF residues in two
103 GLV, i.e. chickpea leaves and spinach leaves which were collected from the local market of Sagar,
104 Madhya Pradesh (India). Studies on the washing of GLVs using conventional chromatographic
105 techniques have been reported by researchers for about a decade [21–25]. The conventional
106 chromatographic methods are very sensitive, efficient and accurate but they are not counted under
107 green techniques due to the use of toxic solvents like methanol and acetonitrile [26]. Additionally,
108 they are expensive and time-consuming due to the number of analytical steps involved [27].

109 In the present research work MCF, ICP, DM and PFF were simultaneously separated using
110 micellar liquid chromatography (MLC) with a photodiode array detector (PDA). The MLC
111 technique used here is a green chromatographic technique because the mobile phase used in this
112 technique is an aqueous solution of the micellar phase. Besides its greenness, it is less expensive
113 and less time-consuming due to the direct injection of samples without any sample pretreatment
114 other than filtration. In the present study, two GLVs (spinach and chickpea leaves) were tested for
115 the presence of insecticide residues of MCF, ICP, DM and PFF respectively, after washing with
116 different easy washing methods. Five washing methods were applied on spinach and chickpea
117 leaves i.e., normal water washing (NW), lukewarm water washing (LW), lemon juice water

118 washing (LJW), common salt water washing (CSW) and commercially available fruit-vegetable
119 ozonizer with normal water (OW). After washing, post-wash water and washed vegetable samples
120 were examined individually for the presence of selected insecticide.

121 **2. Material and method**

122 **2.1. Chemicals and instrumentation**

123 The analytical standard 98–99% pure MCF, ICP, DM, and PFF insecticide standard
124 samples were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Mumbai (India). To prepare the micellar mobile
125 phase and to maintain the pH of the mobile phase, 99% pure sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and
126 analytical grade sodium dihydrogen phosphate ($\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) buffer were obtained from
127 Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai (India). HPLC grade solvents 1-propanol, 1-butanol, 1-
128 pentanol and methanol, $\approx 37\%$ hydrochloric acid (HCl) and $>99.0\%$ pure sodium hydroxide
129 (NaOH) for pH balance of the mobile phase were purchased from Rankem, RFCL, New Delhi
130 (India). For the preparation of solutions including mobile phase and analytical samples, HPLC
131 grade water was obtained from Indion Lab-Q Ultra water purification system, Ion Exchange
132 (India) Ltd., Mumbai (India). $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ nylon membrane filters used for the filtration of solutions
133 were from Micron Separation Inc., Westboro, MA (USA).

134 Solubilizing of standard analytes was accomplished by ultrasonic bath from Ultrasons-H,
135 Selecta, Barcelona (Spain). An analytical weighing scale was used from Mettler Toledo India Pvt.
136 Ltd., Mumbai (India) to weigh the chemicals and real samples. The pH of the micellar mobile
137 phase was measured using a digital pH meter used was from pH-102/103 Contech, Instruments
138 Ltd., Mumbai (India). The HPLC used was a Shimadzu Corporation (Shimadzu Prominence),
139 Kyoto (Japan) with an isocratic pump LC-20 AT, auto-sampler SIL-20AC, a photodiode array

140 detector SPD-M20A, 190-800 nm, and a Shimadzu C₁₈ analytical column, dimension of 250 mm
141 length × 4.6 mm internal diameter with 5 µm particle size.

142 **2.2. Chromatograph and chromatographic conditions for analysis**

143 For the analysis of selected insecticides, the micellar liquid chromatographic method was
144 used. The HPLC was used with a micellar mobile phase containing 0.065 M SDS-2% 1-propanol
145 and 0.01 M NaH₂PO₄ buffered to pH 7. The sample injection volume was kept at 20 µL. The
146 aqueous micellar mobile phase flow rate was set at 1 mL/min. under an isocratic mode. The
147 software Shimadzu LC Solution software version 1.22 SP1 operated and controlled the
148 chromatographic system. The tables, charts, chromatograms, and diagrams were prepared using
149 MS Excel and Origin Pro 2018 software.

150 **2.3. Standard stock solution preparation**

151 Standard stock solutions of 100 ppm for MCF, ICP, DM and PFF were prepared by
152 weighing 1 mg standard accurately and transferred into 10 mL volumetric flasks. To achieve 100
153 ppm concentration 10 mL of ultrapure Type-I grade water and methanol were added, respectively.
154 The solutions were ultra-sonicated for 10 min. with an ultrasonic water bath to dissolve standards
155 completely. Then prepared stock solutions were kept under the refrigerator until used.

156 **2.4. Real sample collection and processing**

157 The spinach and chickpea samples were collected from the local vegetable market of Sagar
158 city, Madhya Pradesh (India) following the same strategy as described by Bhamdare et al., 2022
159 with minor modifications [28]. Only one sample of spinach and chickpea was collected from all
160 four markets consisting of eight samples numbered I-IV for spinach and V-VIII for chickpea.
161 These vegetables were selected because they are the main leafy vegetables consumed in this region

162 from September to November and pesticide/insecticide treatment is frequent (around 4-5 cycles
163 per harvesting). The collected samples were packed in inert sterile polyethylene bags to prevent
164 further contamination and immediately transferred to the laboratory. Healthy leaves were selected
165 for the best analytical results and the samples were sorted manually with hands by wearing hand
166 gloves. The samples were then prepared for further analysis in the laboratory. The blank samples
167 for all the examined GLVs were grown in the university horticulture garden without any
168 insecticide treatment. Spinach and chickpeas were grown in the University garden through organic
169 farming without pesticides to serve as a control sample.

170 **2.5. Spiked sample preparation for optimization of time and concentration of washing** 171 **solutions**

172 500 g of fresh hand-sorted blank chickpea and spinach leaves were taken separately and
173 sprayed with 10 ppm of selected insecticides. After spraying, they were left for 1 hour for complete
174 absorbance of insecticide by the leaves. After 1 hour, chickpea and spinach leaves were divided
175 into 50 parts (each part has 10 g). All fifty vegetable samples of spinach and chickpea leaves were
176 washed by dipping and rinsing in five different types of water i.e., NW (100 mL), LW (100 mL)
177 between 37°C to 40°C, LJW (100 mL by adding 1 mL lemon juice), CSW (100 mL by adding 1 g
178 common salt) and ozonizer (using 100 mL normal water), and for different period of time i.e, 2, 4,
179 6, 8 and 10 min respectively. After fixing the washing time, the next step of this analysis was to
180 wash the chickpea and spinach samples in different concentrations of LJW and CSW. After
181 washing, post-wash water remained after all five methods were collected in 100 mL amber glass
182 volumetric flasks separately, labeled, and refrigerated immediately at 4°C until the
183 chromatographic analysis. Post-wash vegetable samples were also collected after washing.

184 **2.6. Real sample preparation of spinach and chickpea leaves**

185 50 g of fresh hand-sorted chickpea and spinach leaves were taken separately and divided
186 into five parts (each part 10 g). Then, all real samples were prepared following the same strategy
187 as spiked sample preparation.

188 **3. Result and discussion**

189 **3.1. Selection of chromatographic conditions**

190 The analysis in MLC generally starts with the selection of suitable pH. The selection of
191 optimum pH depends on the pKa of the analyte which decides its ionization state. In the present
192 study the pKa for MCF (pKa=4.4), ICP (pKa= 1.6), DM (pKa=NA) and PFF (pKa=1.6) which are
193 ionizable compounds. It is well-established that C18 columns have a working pH range between
194 2.5 and 7.5. Therefore, the pH range for the present study was also set between 3 and 7. During
195 the study, it was found that the neutral form of all the analytes was predominant in the selected pH
196 range which was based on the retention behaviour. MLC conducted using 0.1 M SDS buffered to
197 pH 3, 5, and 7 showed minor variations in the retention time (Rt) of the analyte. Because neutral
198 pH 7 was good for the life of the column, therefore pH 7 was finally selected as the optimum pH
199 for further chromatographic analysis.

200 The hydrophobicity and hydrophilicity of selected analytes were determined based on the
201 octanol-water partition coefficient ($\log P_{o/w}$) for MCF; -0.2, ICP; 0.57, DM: 0.78 and PFF; 4.6
202 indicating that MCF is hydrophilic while ICP, DM are slightly hydrophobic and PFF is
203 hydrophobic in nature. The study conducted by Dubey et al., 2014 shows that using a C₁₈ column
204 and pure sodium dodecyl sulfate results in broad peaks and poor resolution [29]. To overcome this

205 problem and improve the chromatographic parameter like efficiency (N) a small amount of short-
206 chain alcohols (1-propanol, 1-butanol, and 1-pentanol) could be added to the mobile phase.

207 The hybrid mobile phases consisting of 0.05 M SDS- 2% 1-propanol, 0.1 M SDS-2% 1-
208 propanol, and 0.15 M SDS-2% 1-propanol at pH 7 were tested. When 2% 1-propanol was added
209 to 0.15 M SDS, the R_t of the analytes decreased rapidly and the compound eluted in the dead time.
210 On the other hand, a higher amount of 1-propanol was needed to decrease the R_t in the case of
211 0.05 M SDS. In search of an optimum mobile phase for simultaneous analysis of selected
212 insecticides, 0.065 M SDS with 2% 1-propanol was found adequate because using this mobile
213 phase all the insecticides were well resolved within adequate time. The chromatographic
214 parameters observed while using the optimized mobile phase (R_t , N, B/A) were; MCF (3.5, 1936,
215 1.2), ICP (6.1 2032, 1.5), DM (7.4, 1968, 1.8) and PFF (11.6, 2267, 2). The mobile phase 0.065 M
216 SDS-2% 1-propanol, 0.01 M NaH_2PO_4 buffered to pH 7 was selected to carry out further
217 chromatographic analysis.

218 **3.2. Method validation**

219 The method was validated following the SANTE/11,312/2021 and International Council for
220 Harmonisation (ICH) guidelines, including limits of detection and quantification, precision and
221 trueness [30], specifically dedicated to the determination of pesticide residues in food and feed
222 samples.

223 **3.2.1. Specificity/selectivity**

224 Under the optimized chromatographic condition, the peaks of selected insecticides i.e. MCF,
225 ICP, DM and PFF were well separated and free from interference from the solvent front eluting at
226 the head of a chromatograph. In GLVs, washed water, and crushed samples, the first peak

227 corresponding to MCF was eluted at 3.5 min., whereas the matrix from crushed leaves was eluted
228 between 2.5 to 3 min. To evaluate the specificity and selectivity of selected insecticides, spinach
229 leaves washed [Figure 1 (a) and Figure 1 (b)] and crushed [Figure 1 (c) and Figure 1 (d)] matrix
230 were spiked with a mixture of MCF, ICP, DM and PFF (10 mg/kg).

231 3.2.2. Linearity

232 To study the linearity of MCF, ICP, DM and PFF calibration curves were constructed for
233 individual compounds using the measured area of chromatographic peaks at eight (n=8) increasing
234 concentrations ranging from 0.05 to 10 µg/mL in spiked GLVs (spinach). The slope, y-intercept,
235 coefficient of determination (r^2), and relative standard deviation (RSD%) were calculated using
236 the least square linear regression method and presented in Table 1. The calibration curve was
237 linear within the analyzed concentrations. The determination coefficient was in the range of 0.997–
238 0.999 and the RSD% was 3.1-5.8% for selected insecticides which is less than the maximal value
239 indicated by the guideline.

240 3.2.3. Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ)

241 The limits of detection and limits of quantification for all the selected insecticides were
242 calculated following the 3.3s criterion and 10 s criterion (3 times and 10 times the standard
243 deviation of the lowest concentration solution included in the calibration divided by the slope of
244 the calibration curve) respectively. The obtained results were based on the relative standard
245 deviation of the response and slope of the calibration curve containing selected insecticide in a
246 concentration range close to the limits of quantification. The compounds have limits of detection
247 and limit of quantification in the range of 0.03 - 0.09 mg/kg and 0.05 - 0.20 mg/kg, respectively
248 (Table 1).

249 **3.2.4. Trueness and precision**

250 The intra- and inter-day trueness and precision of the proposed method were determined
251 for MCF, ICP, DM and PFF with GLV (spinach) by spiking at three concentration levels lowest
252 quantification level, middle quantification level, and upper quantification level. The intra-day
253 values were determined by analyzing six samples on the same day. Inter-day analysis corresponds
254 to the average of five measurements of the intra-day values taken over 3 month period.
255 Calculations of the closeness of agreement and dispersion were as previously detailed [32]. The
256 obtained results are shown in **Table 2**. Results for relative recovery (96.3–99.8%) and dispersion
257 (<6.3%) were inside the acceptance criteria from the guideline (70–120%) and the value provided
258 by the SANTE/11312/2021 guideline [30].

259 **3.2.5. Robustness**

260 The robustness of the method was examined by replicate injections ($n = 6$) of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
261 concentration of MCF, ICP, DM and PFF by introducing small changes in the SDS concentration
262 (0.055–0.075 M), 1-propanol (1.8–2.2%) and pH (6.8–7.2) of the mobile phase. This parameter
263 was examined for each selected insecticide in the optimized mobile phase. Insignificant differences
264 in peak areas and less variability in retention time were observed. The obtained results indicate
265 that the selected factors remain unaffected by small variations in these parameters (RSD <6%).

266 **4. Analysis of real sample**

267 The developed chromatographic method has been applied to know the presence of selected
268 insecticides in all collected samples. During the analysis, MCF was present in spinach, while ICP
269 was found in chickpea leaves. Other investigated insecticides PFF and DM were not detected in
270 any of the samples most probably due to absence, low concentration or they were present in such

271 a concentration which was beyond the instrumental detection limit. Therefore, further
272 investigation, i.e. washing techniques, were only applied for MCF and ICP in spinach and chickpea
273 leaves respectively.

274 **4.1. Effect of time on the washing of insecticide residue**

275 Two types of foods are commonly used in human dietary plans i.e. vegetarian and non-
276 vegetarian. In India, both are common with around 30% of Indians being pure vegetarian and other
277 being of mixed category. In vegetarian foods, GLVs are acknowledged as a blessing for a safe and
278 healthier life and have been in use for centuries. They are an essential part of the diet to meet the
279 daily nutrient requirements. GLVs are also considered high-risk crops because they can be used
280 fresh as in a salad or can be cooked/processed as per the interest of the consumer. It was also
281 observed in many roadside eateries that they do not wash GLVs and use them directly. As already
282 discussed in the introduction section, different types of pesticides and insecticides are used on
283 GLVs to get rid of insects or pests. The usual process of cleaning GLVs is washing them with
284 normal water. This is not particularly an effective and protective procedure because harmful
285 insecticides may persist on the surface of GLVs.

286 Therefore, in the present research work, different household methods were applied to wash
287 the GLVs to see their effectiveness in washing. In common household practice, people think that
288 pesticide residues could be reduced by washing with normal water within 5 min. During the
289 preliminary investigation of spinach and chickpea leaves only MCF and ICP were detected in most
290 of the collected samples. Therefore household washing techniques were applied to reduce MCF
291 and ICP insecticide residues in chickpea and spinach leaves. The samples were treated with NW,
292 LW, 1% LJW, 1% CSW and OW for different time intervals i.e. 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 min. using fresh

293 water for every wash and the percentage of residual removal was reported [Figure 2 (a) and
294 Figure 2 (b)].

295 During the investigation, it was observed that insecticide residue removal was affected by
296 washing duration for example MCF in spinach samples were removed 22%, 40%, 46%, 42%, 34%,
297 and ICP in chickpea leaves was removed 26%, 44%, 50%, 47%, 37% when washed with NW for
298 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 min. using fresh water for each wash, respectively. After washing with LW for
299 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 min. using fresh water for every wash, MCF was removed 28%, 41%, 63%, 58%,
300 46%, and ICP was removed 33%, 44%, 67%, 62%, 49%, respectively. Following a similar
301 procedure, when the samples were washed with ozonizer, it removed 32%, 44%, 70%, 64%, 53%
302 of MCF, and the ICP residual removal was 39%, 47%, 73%, 68%, 56%, respectively. By washing
303 with CSW for the same time interval, the percentage of MCF removal was 25%, 40%, 54%, 46%,
304 39%, while in the case of ICP it was removed 27%, 44%, 57%, 49%, 43%, respectively. MCF
305 removal was 28%, 40%, 69%, 64%, 58%, and ICP removal was 32%, 44%, 71%, 67%, 53% when
306 washed with lemon water for 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10 min., respectively. Among all five washing
307 techniques, maximum insecticide removal was observed when spinach and chickpea samples were
308 washed for 6 min. Therefore 6 min. washing time was considered adequate for the removal of
309 MCF and ICP from spinach and chickpea leaves, respectively.

310 4.2. Effect of LJW and CSW concentration on the washing of insecticide residue

311 Normal water is a common washing method for GLVs in any kitchen. Insecticides are
312 known for their hydrophobic compounds and are not easily washed off with normal water.
313 Therefore, researchers and scientists have reported different washing methods and techniques to
314 see their effectiveness for pesticide or insecticide removal from vegetables. Different methods
315 were reported by researchers which include baking powder (NaHCO_3) [32,33], vinegar

316 (CH₃COOH), potassium permanganate (KMnO₄) [32], chlorine solution [33], and lemon water
317 (C₃H₃Cl₄N₆O₄) and commercial ozonizer [34], etc. for vegetables but no research group has used
318 these washing techniques in green spinach and chick GLVs. However, no one studied the
319 effectiveness of washing techniques, including LW, 1% LJW, 1% CSW, and OW on spinach
320 leaves. On the other hand, chickpea leaves are the new matrix, and for the first time, they were
321 analyzed to detect the presence of MCF, ICP, DM, and PFF. There are no concentration variables
322 for NW, LW and OW; therefore, the concentration of LJW and CSW was only varied to know the
323 effective concentration of these solutions to get rid of insecticide residues of MCF and ICP in
324 spinach and chickpea leaves, respectively.

325 The concentration of the washing solution was fixed in this experiment. Three
326 concentrations 0.5%, 1%, and 1.5% were selected for LJW and CSW where chickpea and spinach
327 samples were treated with the same for 6 min. (fixed previously) [Figure 3 (a) and Figure 3 (b)].
328 When the samples were washed with a 0.5% concentration of washing solutions, it was not much
329 efficient for both insecticides and only reduced 46% and 38% of MCF and 43% and 36% of ICP
330 residues respectively. When the samples were washed with 1% LJW and CSW, 67% and 63% of
331 MCF residues were removed, and the percentage of ICP residue removal was 64 and 61,
332 respectively. Finally, after washing with 1.5% LJW and CSW the pesticide removal rate was
333 slightly decreased as compared to 1% LJW and CSW washing found 69% and 65% for MCF and
334 66% and 62% for ICP respectively. Thus, 1% concentration was considered more efficient than
335 the other two concentrations.

336 Among all treatments, LJW showed better insecticide reduction capability than CSW,
337 while ozone removed more insecticide residues than LJW. Similarly, the results for NW and LW
338 showed that LW reduced more ICP and MCF residues in comparison to NW. Thus, it could be

339 concluded that common salt has shown better efficiency for removing insecticide residues from
340 spinach and chickpeas compared to LJW. However, it is less efficient in comparison to ozonizer
341 but the effectiveness of CSW is close to it. Therefore, CSW washing method for 6 min. has been
342 fixed to analyse the real samples under the developed chromatographic condition.

343 **4.3. Evaluation of pesticide residues in GLVs**

344 All eight GLV samples were numbered in roman as I-IV for spinach and V-VIII for
345 chickpea were collected from the selected sites and analyzed to detect the presence of MCF, ICP,
346 DM and PFF using the MLC-PDA technique. The chromatographic analysis of analyzed samples
347 revealed that out of eight samples, three samples (II, III, and IV) showed the presence of MCF,
348 while two samples (VI and VIII) were found positive for the presence of ICP. The found
349 concentration of MCF in spinach samples numbered II, III and IV were 1.6 mg/kg, 3.2 mg/kg, and
350 4.2 mg/kg respectively. On the other hand, chickpea samples numbered VI and VIII have shown
351 the presence of ICP at 4.3 mg/kg and 6 mg/kg respectively.

352 The spinach sample which has shown the maximum concentration of MCF (4.2 mg/kg)
353 and chickpea leaves shown the maximum concentration of ICP (6 mg/kg) have been further treated
354 with different washing solutions to know the percentage removal of insecticide residues.

355 Therefore in the present study, the research group investigated the effects of washing with
356 NW, LW, 1% CSW, 1% LJW, and OW to wash chickpea and spinach leaves for 6 min. (which
357 has been optimized before in *sec. 4.1.*). The washed water was collected in a clean container for
358 chromatographic analysis. After filtration with a 0.45 μm filter, different washes of chickpea and
359 spinach were analyzed by an MLC-PDA detector.

360 The representative chromatograms of 6 min. washing of spinach and chickpea leaves has
361 been shown in the form of a 3D graph for comparative assessments among different washing

362 techniques [Figure 4 (a) and Figure 4 (c)]. The effectiveness of washing techniques was cross-
363 checked by crushing the GLV samples obtained after different washings steps. They were also
364 analyzed to know the concentration of insecticide residues (MCF and ICP) left on the surface after
365 washing and systematic residue inside the cuticles of GLVs [Figure 4 (b) and Figure 4(d)].

366 The extent of residue reduction by washing depends on the physiochemical properties of
367 the insecticides such as solubility, rate constant, and octanol-water partition coefficient ($P_{o/w}$).
368 Washing leads to the reduction of hydrophilic insecticide residues which are present on the surface
369 of GLVs. Simple washing techniques can wash off surface residues, whereas systemic residues
370 which have penetrated the cuticle layer are slightly affected. Some pesticides and pyrethroids are
371 nonsystemic, adhered only to the upper surface, and easily removed by the water [35]. Thus,
372 washing significantly affects the removal of residues in several vegetables depending on the
373 hydrophilic or hydrophobic nature of the pesticide. Washing GLVs with normal water is a routine
374 practice in every household. In some roadside eateries, this practice is uncommon. People involved
375 there hardly wash vegetables even with normal water. When chickpea and spinach were washed
376 with NW and the water wash was analyzed with an MLC method, it showed the concentration of
377 ICP was 1.22 mg/kg and MCF was 0.32 mg/kg. The concentrations obtained for ICP and MCF in
378 the crushed samples were 1.82 mg/kg and 0.53 mg/kg, respectively. The results show that NW is
379 not effective for washing GLVs. Also, some people do not recommend washing GLVs in CSW as
380 it slightly dulls the GLV colour but less in comparison to potassium permanganate and vinegar
381 solutions. Lemon is the main natural citric ingredient of every household. 1% lemon juice (1 mL)
382 is effective for washing ICP while less effective for the reduction of MCF residues in chickpeas.
383 Around 2.3 mg/kg of ICP was found in chickpeas LJW wash, which is quite high from the
384 maximum residue safety limit of 2 mg/kg. On the other hand, 0.46 mg/kg MCF residues were

385 detected in the acidic wash of spinach showing its less effectiveness for MCF removal. In the
386 crushed samples of chickpea, the concentration of ICP found was 0.6 mg/kg, while the spinach
387 crushed sample was washed with lemon juice and was found positive for 0.52 mg/kg concentration
388 of MCF.

389 Talking about ozonizer, it is effective for removing insecticides/pesticide residues from the
390 surface as well as cuticles of GLVs to some extent the rate of ICP and MCF removal was around
391 1.63 mg/kg and 0.98 mg/kg respectively. In the case of, chickpea leaves and spinach samples
392 which were washed with ozonizer and crushed have shown the presence of ICP in chickpea leaves
393 are 0.67 mg/kg and MCF in spinach leaves was 0.62 mg/kg.

394 The results obtained in normal water and lukewarm water crushed samples of chickpeas
395 show that both methods are not much effective for washing ICP residues in chickpeas. Similarly,
396 MCF was also not washed off from spinach as it has also shown around a reasonable concentration
397 of MCF in normal and lukewarm water crushed samples.

398 **5. Conclusion**

399 In the present study, MLC coupled with a PDA detector was developed to simultaneously
400 determine MCF, ICP, DM and PFF in spinach and chickpea samples grown around Sagar city
401 (India). The chromatographic examination of marketed spinach and chickpea samples has shown
402 the presence of MCF and ICP, and none of them were found positive for DM and PFF. Therefore
403 washing techniques were only performed for both of them. The developed chromatographic
404 method is green in nature as it uses low-toxicity solvents and also reduces the amount of post-
405 analysis waste, which is very important from an environmental point of view. The obtained GLVs
406 (complex matrix) can be directly injected into the chromatographic system without applying
407 extraction techniques i.e. liquid-liquid extraction, solid phase extraction, QuEChERS, microwave-

408 assisted, ultrasonic assisted, etc. which are time-consuming as well as costly. The developed
409 method is fundamental for those laboratories which are located in underdeveloped and developing
410 countries and require analytical methodologies with low impact on the environment. All four
411 insecticides were separated and detected in the GLVs within the separation time of 11.5 min. with
412 satisfactory precision and accuracy (< 6.3).

413 From the results of this study, it could be concluded that acidic wash, basic wash, and
414 ozonizer can be used as washing techniques for the reduction of superficial as well as systematic
415 residues of ICP and MCF. They are as effective as potassium permanganate and vinegar. But
416 common salt and lemon water have the benefit over vinegar and KMnO_4 in the aspect that it will
417 result in a bright color on the GLVs after the treatment. Available in every kitchen and also have
418 excess to lower socioeconomic classes which could not afford potassium permanganate and
419 vinegar.

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536 **Figure Captions**

537 **Figure 1 (a).** Chromatogram of spinach wash without any insecticide treatments (blank)

538 **Figure 1 (b).** Chromatogram of spinach matrix spiked with 10 mg/kg of MCF, ICP, DM and PFF

539 **Figure 1 (c).** Chromatograms of spinach crushed blank matrix.

540 **Figure 1 (d).** Chromatograms of spinach crushed matrix spiked with 10 mg/kg of MCF, ICP, DM
541 and PFF.

542 **Figure 2 (a).** Removal of MCF residue with time.

543 **Figure 2 (b).** Removal of ICP residue with time.

544 **Figure 3 (a).** Removal of MCF residue with concentration.

545 **Figure 3 (b).** Removal of ICP residue with concentration.

546 **Figure 4 (a).** 3D Chromatograms obtained by the analysis of spinach leaves washed and treated
547 with NW, LW, 1% LJW, 1% CSW, and OW using optimized mobile phase for detection
548 of MCF residue.

549 **Figure 4 (b).** 3D Chromatograms obtained by the analysis of crushed spinach leaves treated with
550 NW, LW, 1% LJW, 1% CSW, and OW using optimized mobile phase for detection of
551 MCF residue.

552 **Figure 4 (c).** 3D Chromatograms obtained by the analysis of chickpea leaves washed and treated
553 with NW, LW, 1% LJW, 1% CSW, and OW using optimized mobile phase for detection
554 of ICP residue.

555 **Figure 4 (d).** 3D Chromatograms obtained by the analysis of chickpea leaves treated with NW,
556 LW, 1% LJW, 1% CSW, and OW using optimized mobile phase for detection of ICP
557 residue.

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